

Target Product Profiles of Laboratory and Data Analytical Frameworks for Genotyping to Monitor Antimalarial Efficacy

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Key words

Genotyping, molecular correction, therapeutic efficacy studies, malaria, *Plasmodium falciparum*, antimalarial

Abstract

Therapeutic efficacy studies (TESs) are the standard to evaluate antimalarial drug efficacy and guide malaria treatment policy. TESs are particularly relevant now, with resistance to first-line regimens emerging in sub-Saharan Africa. For TESs, a range of parasite genotyping and data analyses are available for genotype correction, a process to distinguish whether recurrent parasitemia after therapy is due to recrudescence of initially infecting parasites (treatment failure) or a new infection. The choice of methods for laboratory genotyping and data analyses can have a large effect on how outcomes are classified, and thereby on trial results. The currently recommended and most widely used laboratory and analytical methods for TES genotyping do not incorporate recent methodological advances and can produce biased results. As such current TES results can be difficult to interpret, especially in areas with high malaria transmission, such as much of sub-Saharan Africa. Thus, improving the accuracy and reliability of TES genotyping and data analysis are a major priority. To that end, we present target product profiles that outline key specifications for genetic data generation, processing, and data analysis, with the goal of creating rigorous and consistent community standards. Primary recommended specifications for laboratory methods include high sensitivity, specificity, and reproducibility, and guidance on the number and genetic diversity of targets; criteria which are best and likely only met by amplicon sequencing. Primary recommendations for data analysis methods include high classification accuracy, accounting for errors in genotyping, and accounting for alleles matching by chance. All laboratory and data analysis methods used should be systematically validated and publicly documented so that TES results, which have major policy implications, can be relied upon for sound programmatic decision making.

Background

The ability to treat and cure *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria constitutes a centuries-long arms race between the development of new antimalarial compounds and the malaria parasites' evolution to resist these drugs. The most recent class of antimalarials, the highly efficacious artemisinin-based combination therapies (ACTs), has contributed to a dramatic decline in the malaria burden over the past 20 years.¹ However, partial resistance to artemisinin derivatives in combination with resistance to some partner drugs resulted in therapeutic clinical failures in Southeast Asia and now threatens gains made in sub-Saharan Africa, where the malaria burden is highest.²

Therapeutic efficacy studies (TESs) are the primary means by which antimalarial drug efficacy is monitored under programmatic conditions and choices of therapy are determined.³ In these trials, patients with microscopy-confirmed *P. falciparum* infection are treated with antimalarials and followed for 4-6 weeks to assess clinical and parasitological responses to treatment. Blood samples are collected from patients on the day they enroll, before treatment (Day 0), and routinely for the remainder of the follow-up period. Treatment failure is defined as slow or incomplete clearance in the three days immediately following treatment, or recurrence of parasitemia during follow-up despite initial clearance of detectable parasitemia.

Antimalarial trials are complicated by the possibility, especially in high transmission settings, of new blood-stage infections acquired via ongoing exposure to infectious mosquito bites and subsequent sporozoite inoculation during follow-up, which can confound assessment of treatment efficacy. Thus, cases of recurrent *P. falciparum* parasitemia can be due to either (a) recrudescence, *i.e.*, true treatment failure, (b) new infection, *i.e.*, an infection developing from a new mosquito inoculation, or (c) a mixture of both recrudescence and newly inoculated clones. Genotype correction (also known as molecular correction) is performed to distinguish between these situations.^{3,4} Paired samples from the same patient are collected on Day 0 and the day of recurrence of microscopically detectable parasites. Parasites from both samples are genotyped and compared to distinguish recrudescence from new infection (or a mixture of both), with matched genotypes implying recrudescence. In the corrected efficacy estimate - the primary outcome of the TES - new infections are not considered treatment failures and do not contribute to the failure rate. While genotype correction is straightforward in principle, TES outcomes are often classified based on subjective and unreliable genotyping methods, as well as ad-hoc, non-standardized data analysis, leading to potentially biased and inconsistent results.^{2,5-11}

Distinguishing recrudescence events from new infections in high transmission areas poses particular challenges due to high rates of recurrent parasitemia and a high prevalence of infections containing multiple genetically distinct clones (polyclonal infections).^{6,7} Characterization of a limited number of length polymorphic loci (*e.g.*, merozoite surface proteins and microsatellites) using gel or capillary electrophoresis has been historically used as the standard for distinguishing recrudescence from new infection.¹² However, the discriminatory power of these loci can be limited in high-transmission settings, in part due to limited analytical sensitivity to detect minority alleles and difficulty in generating and reproducibly analyzing length polymorphism data. In response, recent (2021) World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines advocate for the integration of amplicon deep sequencing and probabilistic modeling to enhance the diagnostic accuracy of genotype correction, especially in high-transmission settings where traditional genotyping methods may be particularly challenging.¹³

Even with accurate genotyping, comparison of genotypes in paired samples is complex. Data analysis methods that perform such comparisons can be broadly divided into two approaches: heuristic, rule-based approaches and statistical approaches, which are either based on a probabilistic model or on hypothesis testing using empirical distributions.^{14,15} The most common rule-based approach is match counting, where a recrudescence is defined when the number of loci for which shared alleles are detected in both samples exceeds a predefined threshold. The current WHO standard, dating back to 2007, is to use a strict 3/3 match counting approach.¹² In this approach, three length polymorphisms are genotyped and the infection is classified as recrudescence if at least one allele of each locus matches between samples from Day 0 and the day of recurrence. Rule-based approaches like these are subject to potential biases. For example, new infections might be misclassified as recrudescence in low transmission areas due to an increased chance of allele matching resulting from low allelic diversity, in particular if only a limited number of loci are included. In high transmission scenarios, many study participants will carry polyclonal infections, *i.e.*, the complexity of infection (COI) will be greater than 1. The presence of multiple circulating

clones can bias results toward recrudescence due to the increased number of alleles from a finite allele pool that are being compared. At the same time, high-parasitemia clones in polyclonal infections can mask lower-parasitemia clones, resulting in undetected alleles and biasing results away from recrudescence. In all settings, biological constraints (such as organ tissue sequestration of clones) and technical limitations (such as PCR amplification bias) can lead to misclassification of recurrent parasitemia.^{4,16–19} Unlike rule-based approaches, statistical approaches have been designed to incorporate factors such as parasite population genetic diversity, polyclonal infections, undetected alleles, and other factors while also providing the ability to express uncertainty of the classification.^{14,15,20,21} These statistical approaches have not yet been widely implemented in TESs.

With the multiple limitations in recommended genotype correction methods for TES (laboratory and data analysis), few available antimalarials to choose from, and no new drugs expected soon, policymakers find themselves needing to make difficult choices with a lack of robust evidence. Underestimating recrudescence can result in continued use of a failing drug, worsening patient outcomes and providing continued selective pressure for resistance. Overestimating recrudescence can result in premature recall of an effective drug, when the availability of choices may be limited and the cost of changing policy substantial. In both cases, incorrect policy decisions will lead to mismanagement of patients, inadequate mitigation of resistance, and sub-optimal use of limited public resources. Consequently, improving the accuracy and reliability of genotype correction for TESs is a major priority for the malaria community. To that end, we present target product profiles (TPPs) that outline key specifications for genetic data generation and processing (*i.e.*, from blood sample to allele calls) and the statistical analysis of these data (*i.e.*, from allele calls to classification and overall study results). The target audience for this document includes national malaria programs, researchers, funders and multilateral organizations who all work together to inform and guide malaria case management policy decisions. Given the likelihood of continued evolution of methods, the TPPs intentionally do not specify that any particular genotyping or data analysis method be used, with the objective that any method rigorously validated to meet these criteria should provide the desired output. However, specific methods are occasionally referenced for clarity or to provide examples.

Methods

Draft TPPs for genotyping assays and statistical analysis frameworks for genotype correction of antimalarial TES were developed with characteristics described as either ‘minimal’ or ‘optimal’. Minimal was defined as the basic characteristics that should be met to produce reliable results for a TES. Optimal was defined as any additional desired characteristics beyond minimal. Experts were selected based on their experience and expertise in the field of genotyping analyses of malaria parasites, including from laboratory and data analysis perspectives. An initial group of experts was convened to discuss and outline the two TPPs: one on laboratory genotyping and the other on data analysis. We defined the scope of the laboratory assay TPP as starting from DNA extraction and ending at defining alleles present in the blood sample, including any data processing or bioinformatics needed to obtain allele calls. We defined the scope of the data analysis TPP as starting from allele calls and ending at final genotype correction results, *i.e.*, whether the infections in participants with recurrent parasitemia were more likely a recrudescence or new infection. Subsequently, experts in the field were engaged to provide additional comments by broadly

soliciting feedback on a volunteer basis, with most of these experts focusing on either the laboratory or data analysis TPP based on their expertise.

Simulations

We performed simple simulations to provide practical guidelines on the number and diversity of genetic loci required to distinguish recrudescence from new infection at a level of accuracy listed in the TPP. Details of the simulations including code and results are provided. In brief, we used a grid of approximately 4000 (2^{12}) heterozygosity (H_e) values with corresponding population allele frequencies; these frequencies were repeated for each locus. For each constructed panel and each complexity of infection (COI) value, we simulated 10,000 sample pairs with and without recrudescence and used the *asterTES* package to classify each pair as a recrudescence or a new infection.²⁰ We assumed alleles had a 90% probability of detection, with a false positive rate of 2%. More details and simulation code are included in the supplemental materials. Classification results were then used to calculate specificity and sensitivity; the smallest H_e value to achieve the desired performance level is presented.

Results

Participants: In total, ten individuals contributed to the initial drafting of the TPPs (first eight and last two authors), followed by 19 additional experts assisting with edits and comments. All the experts are engaged in genetic analyses of malaria parasites, with expertise in *P. falciparum*. Participants were primarily based in Europe and the USA, with 3 participants from Africa. Nineteen participants focused primarily on the laboratory component while ten participants focused on the data analysis component. There was an even breakdown for sex (16/29 female), and all had an advanced degree (PhD or MD). The final TPP for laboratory genotyping is outlined in Tables 1-4 and for statistical analysis in Tables 5-6.

General Characteristics

Intended use: The overall goal of genotype correction in a TES is to distinguish new infections from recrudescence infections. To this end, the goal of the laboratory assay is to generate allele calls. The goal of the statistical analysis framework is to use these allele calls on pairs of samples from the same individual to robustly classify recurrence as a new infection or recrudescence, or alternatively assign an accurate probability for each recurrence classification.

Once individual-level classifications are available, the final analytic step in a trial is to calculate the overall study-level failure rate. Optimally, uncertainty from allele calls through recurrence classification into study-level failure rates would be propagated into the final failure rate calculations. However, an extensive review of the methods for study-level failure rate estimation (e.g., a competing risk approach versus Kaplan–Meier estimator) is outside the scope of this exercise.

Target study population: The target population is malaria patients enrolled in a clinical trial to monitor the efficacy of an antimalarial drug.

Target end users and implementation: The target users may vary based on the logistics of study implementation. For the laboratory assay, users will always include highly qualified staff at well-equipped laboratories for the required methodologies and may include staff at resource-limited laboratories. This includes national public health laboratories, research laboratories, and regional centers of excellence. For the analytical framework, users will include TES data analysts and investigators who will conduct statistical analyses; with appropriate development it should be relatively straightforward to make data analysis widely accessible to users with a range of backgrounds and expertise. To ensure statistical

frameworks meet expectations and encourage uptake, algorithms and code should meet the FAIR criteria for research software.²²

Technical and performance characteristics:

Laboratory TPP: The most important performance criteria were sensitivity in detecting minority clones, specificity of allele calling, number and genetic diversity of targets (including their allelic frequency distributions), and reproducibility of the assay, including replicates between labs. Sensitivity was discussed at length, considering the importance of detecting minor variants at a range of parasitemia levels and the practical limitations of current assays; inadequate sensitivity limits the ability to detect recrudescence clones. Specificity must be sufficient to minimize the probability of false positive alleles resulting in misclassification of a new infection as a recrudescence. Multiple, diverse targets are required to ensure accurate recurrence classification within the population of interest. The number and diversity of targets required may vary considerably depending on COI; thus we performed simulations to create basic guidelines as part of the TPP (Table 4). Ideally, the number and diversity of targets would be sufficient to account for worst case scenarios. Finally, validity of employed assays and their reproducibility on shared samples between labs should be prioritized, for example with the use of an external quality assurance program managed by a third-party organization.

Data Analytic TPP: The most important performance criteria include classification of specificity and sensitivity that account for errors in genotyping, particularly non-detection of minority alleles, and alleles matching by chance. Other criteria include that the statistical algorithm is accurate and consistent, *i.e.*, for a given recurrence, the output of the software results in a stable classification (recrudescence or new infection) or stable per-outcome probabilities with precision improving for increasing numbers of loci. A modular and scalable implementation would allow easy adaptation and extension as new data types (*e.g.*, new genotyping techniques) become available. Implementation should follow best practices in version control and software maintenance to ensure long-term usability and community contributions.

Operational characteristics

Laboratory TPP: Optional criteria for assays include the ability to use a range of blood products, including a dried blood spot since these are easy to collect and maintain. Both low- and high-throughput platforms may be suitable, provided they meet the performance criteria outlined above. However, there was a strong preference for deep sequencing-based assays due to high accuracy, reproducibility, and efficiency, as discussed below. Costs should be reasonable and obtain economies of scale depending on the throughput, *i.e.*, if running a larger number of samples the cost per sample should decrease. Standard training from experienced laboratories to ensure high quality data is needed, in addition to standardized quality assurance and quality control (QA & QC). Genotyping methods that employ equipment that are readily usable for other laboratory activities - synergizing shared costs and training - are preferred.

Data Analytic TPP: Optional criteria for data analysis include code which is freely available, well commented, provides user-friendly tutorials, and is easy to use. The algorithm should be implementable on a standard laptop and not require high performance computing resources. As well as being robust to differences in data quality, sample size, and genetic diversity, the algorithm should perform well across a range of parasite populations of varying COI from low to high transmission scenarios.

Discussion

Accurate monitoring of antimalarial efficacy from TESs depends on accurate genotype correction stemming high quality molecular analysis and appropriate data analysis. This is particularly true in areas with high malaria transmission, where the likelihood of new

infections after therapy is the highest. Importantly, increasing antimalarial resistance is being observed across multiple high-transmission areas of Africa.^{2,23–25} Without methodologic standardization across different settings and studies, it is unclear how to best interpret TES results to inform clinical care and practice. Ensuring methods meet the criteria outlined in the TPPs described here will help improve accuracy and consistency of genotype-corrected trial estimates while also providing appropriate uncertainty around these estimates, necessary to interpret and compare results over time and place. Further, it is essential that laboratory assays and the data analysis methods used to interpret results from these assays are compatible with each other. This includes model assumptions (e.g., genotyping errors modeled by analysis methods should be appropriate for the type of data generated) and more practical considerations (e.g., data output on allele calls can be input directly into analysis software, ideally facilitated by common data standards).²⁶ Any laboratory and data analysis methods used should be systematically validated and its quality publicly documented so that clinical trial results, which have major policy implications, can be trusted. With appropriate design, these two components can provide a seamless evaluation workflow for those implementing TESs to monitor antimalarials- from genotyping methods to data analysis, and finally to drug efficacy estimates - making it straightforward to obtain and report transparent, reproducible, and accurate findings.

The last formal update to genotype correction guidance was published in 2008, with an informal update in 2021.^{12,13} The more recent update aimed to balance the state of science, favoring deep sequencing, and the feasibility of operationalization in malaria endemic settings. Since then, the expanded reach of deep sequencing in malaria endemic settings has greatly improved the context of what is feasible.²⁷ At the same time, recent TESs in high-transmission settings in sub-Saharan Africa have urgently highlighted the weaknesses of the older methods, yielding potentially inaccurate results that have complicated interpretation of the TES, delaying action and potentially contributing to the continued unabated spread of resistant parasites.^{28–33}

Key requirements for laboratory methods include a thorough validation process assessing parameters such as sensitivity in detection of minority alleles from several genetically diverse loci. Failing to detect alleles can result in imperfect detection of recrudescence and underestimation of failure; too few loci or too low diversity in loci can result in successfully treated participants appearing to have recrudescence and overestimation of failure. Either of these issues can have a substantial effect on the final results, and both are potentially exacerbated in areas with high transmission where COI is often high and recurrent parasitemia is common. No laboratory method is perfect, and data analysis methods should account for these limitations and sources of error to the extent possible. However, major advances in sequencing technology and *Plasmodium*-specific targeted sequencing assays have dramatically improved the accuracy and decreased the cost of sequencing-based genotyping in the 27 years since genotype correction was originally proposed.^{4,34–39} Importantly, high throughput sequencing is now available in national public health labs of over 80% of countries in sub-Saharan Africa, several of which are performing *Plasmodium* amplicon sequencing at scale.²⁷ While it is possible that older methods based on length polymorphisms may meet the criteria listed in the TPPs, it is likely that sequence-based methods will provide more accurate, reproducible, and cost-effective results, particularly if a large number of loci are required and/or sequencing of markers of drug resistance is also desired. Moreover, the interpretation of length polymorphic markers analyzed by capillary sequencing is time consuming, difficult, and highly subjective, especially in non-experienced laboratories, limiting the reproducibility of those assays.¹⁰ Sequence-based methods can produce data for a large number of loci simultaneously, making it easier to obtain results in a timely manner.^{39–41} Leveraging existing sequencing platforms may also support overall usage and help build local expertise. Whatever methods are used, it will be important for labs performing assays to have qualified staff and reliable access to affordable reagents, external quality assurance, support for quality control

including standardized controls, and appropriate training resources.

Transforming data from laboratory assays into trusted results requires that estimates produced by data analysis account for sources of genotyping error and uncertainty around classification estimates. Traditionally used data analysis methods based on match-counting do neither, are not easily transferable to different genotyping methods, and can provide inconsistent, biased results.^{20,42} Important considerations for analysis methods, as outlined in the TPPs described here, are that they account for statistical factors such as the expected number of alleles matching by chance in paired samples by taking into account population allele frequencies and COI. Technical factors, such as genotyping errors, also need to be accounted for. If done properly, results should be consistent regardless of the genotyping method used, though more accurate, high-resolution genotyping data should produce more precise estimates. To date, four statistical methods have been proposed, three of which have accompanying software packages.^{14,15,20,21} These software packages may be considered for implementation after appropriate, ideally standardized, benchmarking is performed. Analogous to ongoing efforts for other data analysis tools, benchmarking will enable their full appraisal relative to the data analytic TPP and set a baseline for future method development.²⁶ Accessible implementation of the data analysis method will be important to ensure transparent, reproducible results. For example, fast, easy-to-use genotype correction software available locally and/or via a cloud-based platform would lower the barrier to high quality data analysis and encourage uptake. Even better would be extending this to a modular, integrated workflow for allele calling, genotype correction, study-level inference, and related analyses like associations between treatment failure and molecular markers of antimalarial resistance.

Validation of existing and newly developed methods to generate laboratory data and analyze these data for genotype correction should be evaluated in the context of the TPP framework described, with compliance assessed and documented. For example, sensitivity of the laboratory method for detecting minority alleles can be assessed via standardized controls containing mixtures of *P. falciparum* clones at known proportions; these would ideally be made available by a central facility and used in all laboratories genotyping samples from TEs. Likewise, sensitivity, specificity, and consistency of data analysis methods would benefit from *in silico* experiments using standardized datasets. Methods that do not meet minimum criteria should be avoided, and if used (e.g., due to insurmountable logistical constraints), investigators should interpret final efficacy measures in light of the potential biases introduced.

Estimates of allele frequencies for loci used in genotype correction are important to ensure the accurate analysis of results. These estimates are ideally calculated using all (or, for large studies, a random sample of) Day 0 timepoints, from individuals with and without recurrent parasitemia, if resources allow. Further, *in silico* simulation experiments or bootstrapping of previous datasets can guide determination of how many total samples would need to be genotyped to provide enough precision for allele frequencies that allow for accurate estimation of recrudescence versus new infection status. Other options include incorporating data on allele frequencies from external sources, such as from recent or concurrent molecular studies from nearby sites.

Although we focus on TEs, these guidelines are meant to apply to any study or surveillance activity where antimalarial therapeutic efficacy is a primary outcome and where participants are subject to continuing risk of new infection during the period of follow up. Whereas many TEs are specifically designed to be incorporated as part of routine surveillance, clinical trials of new and candidate drugs typically have larger sample sizes, better resources, and require a higher standard of evidence. As such, clinical trials should, where possible, strive to meet the optimal criteria for all genotyping and statistical analysis components.

As outlined above, some laboratory and data analysis methods have already been designed to account for factors such as genetic diversity, polyclonal infections, undetected alleles, and other genotyping errors. However, there are additional factors that may affect the accuracy of genotype correction, including parasite population structure, latent liver stages at enrollment, completely undetected parasites (e.g., due to organ tissue sequestration of parasites), and persistent gametocytes, which are not easily distinguished from asexual parasites by DNA genotyping.^{4,13} Some of these factors may distort genotype correction at the per-participant level. Fortunately, per-participant precision, while important for detecting associations with treatment failure (such as parasite mutations or plasma drug levels) is not the primary goal of a TES. At the study level, these issues can be mitigated by randomization in multi-arm studies. Single-arm studies are more vulnerable to classification bias, especially if relying on unvalidated genotype correction methods. However, this bias may be addressed using sensitivity analyses or models that go beyond the standard capabilities of current genotype correction software. Some of these advanced capabilities could be integrated into future data analysis tools, likely requiring a revision of the current TPP.

Exclusive use of fragment-length polymorphic loci and simple heuristic-based data analysis methods are no longer supported by the current state of science. Where possible, newer techniques that have been benchmarked and appraised as a core part of TESs should be the standard. It may be of interest to perform traditional genotyping methods in parallel for some studies, to facilitate evaluation of temporal trends including prior studies and provide direct comparison of results from different methods. Evidence that newer methods provide different and (based on rigorous validation) more accurate results should further motivate switching to modern laboratory and data analysis tools and to using their results for the primary analysis of trials and policy decision making.

At this point, it is not clear if the scientific community is well-advised to coalesce around a single set of loci, laboratory assay, and data analytic method that will replace the length-polymorphic markers and match counting from the 2008 formal guidance and 2021 informal update. Fortunately, it is likely that several genotyping and data analysis method combinations will be able to meet the criteria outlined here in the near future, and thus that multiple independent approaches will yield high-quality and similar results. Importantly, one of the key concepts emphasized in this TPP is consistent reporting of uncertainty. If uncertainty is properly measured and reported, results using different laboratory and data analytic methods will more likely be comparable. Consistency in results is critical and will require validation, e.g., via *in silico* simulations, standardized reference samples, and parallel application in real TESs. Moreover, as methods become more sensitive and discriminatory, results should be more robust and stable across different methods. Adherence to the best practices for new genotype correction approaches over the coming years will help build the evidence base around the comparability and robustness of different approaches, setting the stage for the next phase of antimalarial efficacy monitoring.

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Disclaimer

The findings and conclusions in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily represent the official position of the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention or the European Union.

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CITATIONS

1. Bhatt S, Weiss DJ, Cameron E, Bisanzio D, Mappin B, Dalrymple U, Battle KE, Moyes CL, Henry A, Eckhoff PA, Wenger EA, Briët O, Penny MA, Smith TA, Bennett A, et al., 2015. The effect of malaria control on *Plasmodium falciparum* in Africa between 2000 and 2015. *Nature* 526: 207–211
2. Rosenthal PJ, Asua V, Bailey JA, Conrad MD, Ishengoma DS, Kanya MR, Rasmussen C, Tadesse FG, Uwimana A, Fidock DA., 2024. The emergence of artemisinin partial resistance in Africa: how do we respond? *Lancet Infect Dis*: S1473-3099(24)00141–5
3. World Health Organization. Methods for surveillance of antimalarial drug efficacy. Available at: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/9789241597531>. Accessed
4. Snounou G, Beck H-P., 1998. The Use of PCR Genotyping in the Assessment of Recrudescence or Reinfection after Antimalarial Drug Treatment. *Parasitol Today* 14: 462–467
5. Plucinski MM, Hastings IM, Moriarty LF, Venkatesan M, Felger I, Halsey ES., 2021. Variation in Calculating and Reporting Antimalarial Efficacy against *Plasmodium falciparum* in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Systematic Review of Published Reports. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* 104: 1820–1829
6. Greenhouse B, Dikomajilar C, Hubbard A, Rosenthal PJ, Dorsey G., 2007. Impact of Transmission Intensity on the Accuracy of Genotyping To Distinguish Recrudescence from New Infection in Antimalarial Clinical Trials. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 51: 3096–3103
7. Jones S, Plucinski M, Kay K, Hodel EM, Hastings IM., 2020. A Computer Modelling Approach To Evaluate the Accuracy of Microsatellite Markers for Classification of Recurrent Infections during Routine Monitoring of Antimalarial Drug Efficacy. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 64: e01517-19
8. Hastings IM, Felger I., 2022. WHO antimalarial trial guidelines: good science, bad news? *Trends Parasitol* 38: 933–941
9. Greenhouse B, Myrick A, Dikomajilar C, Woo JM, Carlson EJ, Rosenthal PJ, Dorsey G., 2006. Validation of microsatellite markers for use in genotyping polyclonal *Plasmodium falciparum* infections. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* 75: 836–842
10. Schnoz A, Beuret C, Concu M, Hosch S, Rutaihua LK, Golumbeanu M, Nsanzabana C., 2024. Genotyping methods to distinguish *Plasmodium falciparum* recrudescence from new infection for the assessment of antimalarial drug efficacy: an observational, single-centre, comparison study. *Lancet Microbe* 5: 100914
11. Collins WJ, Greenhouse B, Rosenthal PJ, Dorsey G., 2006. The use of genotyping in antimalarial clinical trials: a systematic review of published studies from 1995-2005. *Malar J* 5: 122

12. Medicines for Malaria Venture, World Health Organization., 2008. Methods and techniques for clinical trials on antimalarial drug efficacy : genotyping to identify parasite populations. Informal consultation organized by the Medicines for Malaria Venture and cosponsored by the World Health Organization, 29-31 May 2007, Amsterdam, The Netherlands. : 45
13. World Health Organization. Informal consultation on methodology to distinguish reinfection from recrudescence in high malaria transmission areas. Available at: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/9789240038363>. Accessed
14. Plucinski MM, Morton L, Bushman M, Dimbu PR, Udhayakumar V., 2015. Robust Algorithm for Systematic Classification of Malaria Late Treatment Failures as Recrudescence or Reinfection Using Microsatellite Genotyping. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 59: 6096–6100
15. Plucinski MM, Barratt JLN., 2021. Nonparametric Binary Classification to Distinguish Closely Related versus Unrelated Plasmodium falciparum Parasites. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* 104: 1830–1835
16. Messerli C, Hofmann NE, Beck H-P, Felger I., 2017. Critical Evaluation of Molecular Monitoring in Malaria Drug Efficacy Trials and Pitfalls of Length-Polymorphic Markers. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 61: e01500-16
17. Felger I, Snounou G, Hastings I, Moehrle JJ, Beck H-P., 2020. PCR correction strategies for malaria drug trials: updates and clarifications. *Lancet Infect Dis* 20: e20–e25
18. Juliano JJ, Gadalla N, Sutherland CJ, Meshnick SR., 2010. The perils of PCR: can we accurately “correct” antimalarial trials? *Trends Parasitol* 26: 119–124
19. Jones S, Kay K, Hodel EM, Gruenberg M, Lerch A, Felger I, Hastings I., 2021. Should Deep-Sequenced Amplicons Become the New Gold Standard for Analyzing Malaria Drug Clinical Trials? *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 65: 10.1128/aac.00437-21
20. Gerlovina I, Berube S, Briggs J, Murie K, Murphy M, Wesolowski A, Greenhouse B., 2025. Classification of outcomes in antimalarial therapeutic efficacy studies with Aster. *BioRxiv Prepr Serv Biol*: 2025.04.28.651146
21. Mehra S, Taylor AR, Imwong M, White NJ, Watson JA., 2025. Probabilistic classification of late treatment failure in uncomplicated malaria. medRxiv
22. Barker M, Chue Hong NP, Katz DS, Lamprecht A-L, Martinez-Ortiz C, Psomopoulos F, Harrow J, Castro LJ, Gruenpeter M, Martinez PA, Honeyman T., 2022. Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software. *Sci Data* 9: 622
23. Emiru T, Getachew D, Murphy M, Sedda L, Ejigu LA, Bulto MG, Byrne I, Demisse M, Abdo M, Chali W, Elliott A, Vickers EN, Aranda-Díaz A, Alemayehu L, Behaksera SW, et al., 2023. Evidence for a role of Anopheles stephensi in the spread of drug- and diagnosis-resistant malaria in Africa. *Nat Med* 29: 3203–3211
24. Conrad Melissa D., Asua Victor, Garg Shreeya, Giesbrecht David, Niaré Karamoko, Smith Sawyer, Namuganga Jane F., Katairo Thomas, Legac Jennifer, Crudale Rebecca M., Tumwebaze Patrick K., Nsobya Samuel L., Cooper Roland A., Kanya Moses R., Dorsey Grant, et al., 2023. Evolution of Partial Resistance to Artemisinins in Malaria Parasites in Uganda. *N Engl J Med* 389: 722–732
25. Martinez-Vega R, Ishengoma DS, Gosling R, Rosenthal PJ, Dondorp A, Barnes KI, Nsanzabana C, Djimde AA, Ochola-Oyier LI, Tibenderana J, Chimumbwa J, Golassa L, Kapologwe NA, Mbacham WF, Kanya MR, et al., 2025. Regional action needed to halt antimalarial drug resistance in Africa. *Lancet Lond Engl* 405: 7–10
26. Ruybal-Pesántez S, Amaya-Romero J, Bérubé S, Brazeau NF, Diop MF, Hathaway N, Hendry J, McCann K, Murie K, Murphy M, Niaré K, Phelan J, Schaffner SF, Simkin A, Taylor AR, et al., 2025. Towards an open analysis ecosystem for Plasmodium genomic epidemiology. medRxiv
27. Mboowa G, Tessema SK, Christoffels A, Ndembi N, Tebeje YK, Kaseya J., 2024. Africa in the era of pathogen genomics: Unlocking data barriers. *Cell* 187: 5146–5150
28. Kanya MR, Nankabirwa JI, Ebong C, Asua V, Kiggundu M, Orena S, Okitwi M, Tukwasibwe S, Agaba B, Kyabayinze D, Opigo J, Rutazana D, Binagwa B, Mugwanya E, Babirye S, et al., 2025. Efficacies of artemether-lumefantrine, artesunate-amodiaquine, dihydroartemisinin-piperazine, and artesunate-pyronaridine for the treatment of uncomplicated Plasmodium falciparum malaria in

children aged 6 months to 10 years in Uganda: a randomised, open-label, phase 4 clinical trial. *Lancet Infect Dis*: S1473-3099(25)00407-4

29. Dimbu PR, Labuda S, Ferreira CM, Caquece F, André K, Pembele G, Pode D, João MF, Pelenda VM, Nieto Andrade B, Horton B, Kennedy C, Svigel SS, Zhou Z, Morais JFM, et al., 2024. Therapeutic response to four artemisinin-based combination therapies in Angola, 2021. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 68: e0152523
30. Ebong C, Sserwanga A, Namuganga JF, Kapisi J, Mpimbaza A, Gonahasa S, Asua V, Gudoi S, Kigozi R, Tibenderana J, Bwanika JB, Bosco A, Rubahika D, Kyabayinze D, Opigo J, et al., 2021. Efficacy and safety of artemether-lumefantrine and dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine for the treatment of uncomplicated Plasmodium falciparum malaria and prevalence of molecular markers associated with artemisinin and partner drug resistance in Uganda. *Malar J* 20: 484
31. Moriarty LF, Nkoli PM, Likwela JL, Mulopo PM, Sompwe EM, Rika JM, Mavoko HM, Svigel SS, Jones S, Ntamabyaliro NY, Kaputu AK, Lucchi N, Subramaniam G, Niang M, Sadou A, et al., 2021. Therapeutic Efficacy of Artemisinin-Based Combination Therapies in Democratic Republic of the Congo and Investigation of Molecular Markers of Antimalarial Resistance. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* 105: 1067–1075
32. Gansané A, Moriarty LF, Ménard D, Yerbanga I, Ouedraogo E, Sondo P, Kinda R, Tarama C, Soulama E, Tapsoba M, Kangoye D, Compaore CS, Badolo O, Dao B, Tchwenko S, et al., 2021. Anti-malarial efficacy and resistance monitoring of artemether-lumefantrine and dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine shows inadequate efficacy in children in Burkina Faso, 2017-2018. *Malar J* 20: 48
33. Westercamp N, Owidhi M, Otieno K, Chebore W, Buff AM, Desai M, Kariuki S, Samuels AM., 2022. Efficacy of Artemether-Lumefantrine and Dihydroartemisinin-Piperaquine for the Treatment of Uncomplicated Plasmodium falciparum Malaria among Children in Western Kenya, 2016 to 2017. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 66: e0020722
34. Gruenberg M, Lerch A, Beck H-P, Felger I., 2019. Amplicon deep sequencing improves Plasmodium falciparum genotyping in clinical trials of antimalarial drugs. *Sci Rep* 9: 17790
35. Gondard M, Lane M, Barratt J, Talundzic E, Qvarnstrom Y., 2023. Simultaneous targeted amplicon deep sequencing and library preparation for a time and cost-effective universal parasite diagnostic sequencing approach. *Parasitol Res* 122: 3243–3256
36. de Cesare M, Mwenda M, Jeffreys AE, Chirwa J, Drakeley C, Schneider K, Mambwe B, Glanz K, Ntalla C, Carrasquilla M, Portugal S, Verity RJ, Bailey JA, Ghinai I, Busby GB, et al., 2024. Flexible and cost-effective genomic surveillance of P. falciparum malaria with targeted nanopore sequencing. *Nat Commun* 15: 1413
37. Tessema SK, Hathaway NJ, Teyssier NB, Murphy M, Chen A, Aydemir O, Duarte EM, Simone W, Colborn J, Saute F, Crawford E, Aide P, Bailey JA, Greenhouse B., 2022. Sensitive, Highly Multiplexed Sequencing of Microhaplotypes From the Plasmodium falciparum Heterozygome. *J Infect Dis* 225: 1227–1237
38. Holzschuh A, Lerch A, Nsanzabana C., 2024. Multiplexed nanopore amplicon sequencing to distinguish recrudescence from new infection in antimalarial drug trials. bioRxiv
39. Aranda-Díaz A, Neubauer Vickers E, Murie K, Palmer B, Hathaway N, Gerlovina I, Boene S, García-Ulloa M, Cisteró P, Katairo T, Semakuba FD, Nsengimaana B, Gwarinda H, García-Fernández C, Louie W, et al., 2025. Sensitive and modular amplicon sequencing of Plasmodium falciparum diversity and resistance for research and public health. *Sci Rep* 15: 10737
40. Katairo T, Asua V, Nsengimaana B, Tukwasibwe S, Semakuba FD, Wiringilimaana I, Kagurusi BA, Mwubaha C, Nakasaanya J, Garg S, Kiyaga S, Mbabazi M, Kabbale KD, Ayitewala A, Nsohya SL, et al., 2025. Performance of molecular inversion probe DR23K and Paragon MAD4HatTeR Amplicon sequencing panels for detection of Plasmodium falciparum mutations associated with antimalarial drug resistance. *Malar J* 24: 188
41. Kattenberg JH, Van Dijk NJ, Fernández-Miñope CA, Guetens P, Mutsaers M, Gamboa D, Rosanas-Urgell A., 2023. Molecular Surveillance of Malaria Using the PF AmpliSeq Custom Assay for Plasmodium falciparum Parasites from Dried Blood Spot DNA Isolates from Peru. *Bio-Protoc* 13: e4621

42. Jones S, Kay K, Hodel EM, Chy S, Mbituyumuremyi A, Uwimana A, Menard D, Felger I, Hastings I., 2019. Improving Methods for Analyzing Antimalarial Drug Efficacy Trials: Molecular Correction Based on Length-Polymorphic Markers msp-1, msp-2, and glurp. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 63: e00590-19

TABLES

Table 1- General scope and characteristics of the genotype correction laboratory assay framework

Characteristic	Minimal Requirements	Optimal Requirements	Comments
Intended use	Genotype correction to distinguish recrudescence from new infection	Genotype correction to distinguish recrudescence from new infection Same assay evaluates validated (+/- candidate) molecular markers of drug resistance	Accurate assessment of intermediate measures, such as complexity of infection and allele frequency, are likely necessary to properly evaluate outcomes as discussed in the data analysis TPP.
Target end users	Well-equipped laboratories for required methods with highly qualified staff Genotyping “hubs” in malaria endemic regions; could potentially include private sector	National laboratories or research laboratories in malaria endemic countries	Minimal and optimal here defined from the standpoint of the assay, not its implementation; an optimal assay would require less in the way of infrastructure than a minimal assay.
Target population	Malaria patients enrolled in antimalarial drug clinical trials	Same as minimal	
Application setting	All laboratories with the required equipment and highly trained staff	Laboratories with limited equipment and staff with basic molecular training	Minimal and optimal here defined from the standpoint of the assay, not its implementation; an optimal assay would require less physical and personnel infrastructure than a minimal assay.
Access and usability	Required infrastructure and equipment should be available in regional genotyping hubs in malaria endemic regions	Required infrastructure and equipment should be available in each malaria endemic country performing trials.	From the standpoint of capacity strengthening, it would be ideal to have each country perform its own genotype correction. This consideration needs to be balanced against the likelihood that having fewer, well-resourced labs (e.g., via a framework to support regional hubs) may be more cost-effective and

			produce more reproducible results. Capacity strengthening of national labs could benefit from a standardized plan for certification, training, and procurement of reagents which could be facilitated by appropriate organizations such as WHO and Africa CDC.
Output	The primary outputs for analysis will be allele calls (<i>e.g.</i> , microhaplotype sequences for amplicon sequencing or binned lengths for length polymorphisms). Assays should additionally output raw genetic data (<i>e.g.</i> , FASTQ file for sequencing, .fsa files for capillary electrophoresis length polymorphisms).	Minimal plus measure of uncertainty around allele calls (including for molecular markers of drug resistance, if included), and/or within sample allele frequencies	Additional outputs pertaining to classification are addressed in the analysis TPP.

Table 2 - Performance characteristics of the genotype correction laboratory assay framework

Characteristic	Minimal Requirements	Optimal Requirements	Comments
Analytical sensitivity	<p>Alleles at $\geq 10\%$ within sample allele frequency (WSAF) detectable in at least 95% of samples if clones are from dried blood spots (DBS) with ≥ 100 parasites/μl</p> <p>AND</p> <p>Alleles at $\geq 5\%$ WSAF detectable in at least 95% of samples if clones are from dried blood spots (DBS) with ≥ 500 parasites/μl</p>	<p>Alleles at $\geq 2\%$ WSAF detectable in at least 95% of samples if clones are from DBS with ≥ 100 parasites/μl</p>	<p>Samples from day of recurrence may have parasite densities lower than initial presentation; requirements for sensitivity need to account for these densities.</p> <p>Sensitivity needs to be validated with blinded, mixed-clone control infections replicating sample type and extraction <i>e.g.</i>, for minimal 5% at 100 parasites/μl. An undisclosed subset of mixed controls should contain > 2 clones. Performing evaluation in replicates, <i>e.g.</i>, at least triplicate, is suggested. Initial validation of methods should include samples run at least in triplicate. Evaluation includes allele-calling methods, <i>e.g.</i>, bioinformatic pipelines for sequencing data.</p> <p>Evaluation of sensitivity, specificity, and reproducibility can best be ensured with an external quality assurance program, ideally coordinated by a third party such as WHO. This includes distributing validation materials including mixed-clone controls as described.</p> <p>For length polymorphism only: Because of preferential amplification of shorter amplicons, the</p>

			larger amplicon should be selected as the minority allele and be the same allelic family as the major allele for at least a subset of controls (<i>e.g.</i> , for msp1: 3D7=minority clone, K1=dominant clone).
Analytical specificity (detection of alleles)	95% of alleles	99% Estimates of uncertainty of allele calls are provided, <i>e.g.</i> , probability of being a true positive allele vs. artifact.	Evaluation includes allele calling methods. Evaluation of sensitivity, specificity, and reproducibility can best be tested with validation in multiple laboratories, and continued performance of individual laboratories ensured with an external quality assurance program, ideally coordinated by a third party.
Reported values	For sequencing-based methods: Reads per allele per locus per sample (validation and trial samples). Details of bioinformatic pipeline used, including code, version, any user-specified parameters, <i>i.e.</i> , enough to fully reproduce the allele call results from the raw data. For length polymorphisms: Presence of genotypes per locus per sample (validation and trial samples). Details of allele calling, <i>e.g.</i> , if alleles are binned the strategy employed to select bin width and location, any cutoffs used to distinguish alleles from artifact. This should be enough	For sequencing-based methods: minimal plus probability of allele being a true positive (<i>i.e.</i> , estimates of uncertainty of allele call from the bioinformatic pipeline). For length polymorphisms: minimal plus estimated WSAF for binned alleles per locus per sample and probability of allele being a true positive (<i>i.e.</i> , estimates of uncertainty of allele call).	

	information to fully reproduce the allele call results from the raw data.		
Number and diversity of loci	See Table 4	Meeting criteria such as calculated in Table 4 using simulations parameterized by setting-specific allele frequencies and distribution of complexity of infection, ensuring that the number and diversity of targets is in excess of what is required per setting.	These are guidelines, but careful attention will need to be paid to analysis outcomes to ensure high enough resolution for specific settings. Table 4 should be considered the first iteration to be updated as additional evidence is generated. Note that in practice a panel may contain a larger number of loci to ensure that the minimal number have sufficient diversity in a given setting and to be robust to missing data <i>e.g.</i> , in low parasitemia samples.
Reproducibility of replicates within a lab	<p>Controls (DBS with known composition of single and multiple laboratory clones) should be run in triplicate each time the assay is used: 98% of times the user gets the same set of alleles in monoclonal controls, 80% of times the user gets the same set of alleles in polyclonal controls containing minority WSAF of 10% and 2%.</p> <p>At least 10% of study samples (with a focus on paired Day 0 and recurrence samples) should be run in duplicate and should meet the criteria above.</p>	<p>Controls (DBS with known composition of laboratory clones) 99% of times the user gets the same set of alleles in monoclonal controls, 90% of times the user gets the same set of alleles in polyclonal controls containing minority WSAF of 10% and 2%.</p> <p>All study samples should be run in triplicate and should meet the criteria above. At least 20% of Day 0 and recurrence sample pairs are validated by an external laboratory and should meet the criteria above.</p>	Evaluation of sensitivity, specificity, and reproducibility can best be tested with validation in multiple laboratories, and continued performance of individual laboratories ensured with an external quality assurance program, ideally coordinated by a third party.

Table 3 - Operational characteristics of the genotype correction laboratory assay framework

Characteristic	Minimal Requirements	Optimal Requirements	Comments
Assay format	Low throughput (<i>e.g.</i> , 20 samples)	High throughput (at least 96-well plate or ~90 samples at a time)	
Assay type	Any assay meeting minimal performance criteria above, which could include NGS-based or capillary electrophoresis	NGS-based assay meeting performance criteria above.	
Sample matrix	Dried blood spot (DBS) The assay may work on other sample types such as whole blood.	Same as minimal	
Cost per individual sample replicate (<i>e.g.</i>, Day 0 sample or control, from DNA extraction to allele generation including <i>e.g.</i>, checking of library quality, sequencing, etc.)	Less than USD 100 for all reagents and consumables (<i>i.e.</i> , not including labor) in a regional hub or reference center	Less than USD 25 for all reagents and consumables in a regional hub or reference center Less than USD 50 for all reagents and consumables in most national laboratories	In many low-resource settings, even the optimal requirements listed here may present a significant barrier. Subsidization mechanisms, pooled procurement models, and availability of shared equipment (<i>e.g.</i> , access to local high-throughput sequencers) may further lower cost and improve access.
Wet lab equipment	Hoods Thermocycler Means of detecting alleles (<i>e.g.</i> , capillary electrophoresis or high throughput sequencer) Other equipment as required Dedicated spaces for DNA extraction, mastermix preparation, and handling of post PCR	Hoods Thermocycler NGS Sequencer Automated systems Other equipment as required Dedicated rooms with appropriate airflow for DNA extraction, mastermix preparation, and handling of post PCR material to minimize	Preferable that the equipment has support of and utility for other lab activities to share cost for purchase, maintenance, training, etc.

	material to minimize contamination.	contamination.	
Computational infrastructure needed	For sequencing-based methods: High performance desktop, laptop, or access to cloud-based resource For length polymorphisms: Standard performance desktop or laptop	For sequencing-based methods: Cloud-based resource and high performance laptop are both options	
Assay throughput	200 individual samples (or 100 paired Day 0 and Day of recurrence samples) in 2 months	400 individual samples (or 200 paired Day 0 and Day of recurrence samples) in 2 weeks	Numbers here are just for time estimates; proper implementation will require a combination of Day 0 and paired samples, negative and positive controls, etc.
Training	8 weeks for wetlab technician with general laboratory experience (e.g., PCR) but not with the specific type of assay (e.g., targeted deep sequencing) 4 weeks for wetlab technician with prior domain-area expertise 8 weeks for bioinformatics or analysis (including allele calling) without prior experience 4 weeks for bioinformatics or analysis with prior domain-area expertise	4 weeks for technician without prior experience 2 week for technician with prior experience 4 weeks for bioinformatics or analysis without prior experience 2 weeks for bioinformatics or analysis with prior experience Continuous evaluation and certification	Minimal and optimal here defined from the standpoint of the assay, not implementation; an optimal assay would require less training. Continuous training is required to maintain proficiency. It is worth considering a staff retention policy to retain technicians with experience Evaluation of competence can best be ensured with an external quality assurance program, ideally coordinated by a third party such as WHO.
QA & QC	Sensitivity, specificity, and reproducibility require internal and external validation using controls and replication	Formal quality assurance (EQA) scheme administered by a third party such as WHO.	

	<p>as described above. At a minimum, this will require a set of positive controls with mixes of different laboratory strains at different densities diluted in human blood stored in the sample type used for the assay (<i>e.g.</i>, DBS) sufficient to assess the sensitivity for detecting minority clones at the levels defined above.</p>		
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Table 4. Guidelines for number and diversity of loci required for accurate genotype

correction. Minimal heterozygosity* per locus needed to achieve the classification performance of 95% specificity and 95% sensitivity determined by simulations and classification using a statistical method that accounts for complexity of infection (COI), allele frequency, and imperfect detection of minority alleles.²⁰ For simplicity, the current simulation assumes both samples have the same COI. NA are present when a heterozygosity of 0.95 in all loci is not high enough to achieve 95% sensitivity and specificity. *Heterozygosity is a measure of allelic diversity at the locus. It is defined as the probability that two alleles taken at random from the local population are different, *i.e.*, higher heterozygosity indicates higher diversity.

	COI = 1	COI = 2	COI = 3	COI = 5	COI = 7
3 loci	0.752	NA	NA	NA	NA
6 loci	0.487	0.866	0.950	NA	NA
9 loci	0.353	0.739	0.910	NA	NA
12 loci	0.266	0.593	0.885	NA	NA
15 loci	0.221	0.485	0.839	NA	NA
18 loci	0.190	0.416	0.754	NA	NA
21 loci	0.164	0.362	0.657	0.950	NA
24 loci	0.145	0.316	0.582	0.928	NA

Table 5 - General scope and characteristics of the TES data analysis framework

Characteristic	Minimal Requirements	Optimal Requirements	Comments
Intended use	Framework explicitly designed to analyze genotyping data from participants with recurrent parasitemia to differentiate between recrudescence and new infection.	Same as minimal, with an additional step of providing an estimate of the corrected efficacy rate with corresponding measures of uncertainty.	
Target end users	Data analysts and investigators of therapeutic efficacy studies	Same as minimal	
Target population	Patients with microscopy-confirmed <i>P. falciparum</i> infection enrolled in a therapeutic efficacy study	Same as minimal	
Collection of samples for analysis	For study participants with recurrent malaria, paired samples of malaria infections on Day 0 and Day of recurrence.	Minimal plus all Day 0 samples regardless of recurrence.	Inclusion of additional genotyped Day 0 samples allows for more accurate estimates of allele frequency (and Day 0 population structure), which results in more robust estimates in methods that account for these factors. Suboptimally, estimates can be obtained from other studies in geographic and temporal proximity.
Implementation setting	National malaria control programs, genotyping hubs in malaria endemic regions, sentinel sites for therapeutic surveillance, research laboratories, or any other setting where antimalarial drug efficacy is monitored and EQA is performed	Same as minimal	

<p>Access and usability</p>	<p>The data analytical framework is available as a statistical program/ or script that can be downloaded from a dedicated website or package repository, with straightforward installation and usage instructions. Software should not be operating system specific. Should include a minimally reproducible example dataset to ensure the framework is being correctly implemented. Should have diagnostic messages and verbose mode to assist users as they run through the workflow.</p>	<p>Same as the minimal, but in addition to being available for download, the analytical framework is also accessible as a free web-based interface with an easy-to-use GUI (e.g., processed genotyping data are uploaded and results, including any QC, are returned). Software is actively maintained. Comprehensive documentation, tutorials, and examples are available to guide users through each step, and an intuitive workflow is included to ensure users can quickly begin using the framework. French and Portuguese instructions are available.</p>	
<p>Structure</p>	<p>The framework has a transparent and easy-to-follow structure.</p>	<p>Same as the minimal version, but with a modular structure allowing individual execution of each component of the overall analysis pipeline. It includes a developer manual to facilitate extensions and modification adjustments.</p>	
<p>Components</p>	<p>An algorithm to characterize (provide a categorical classification or probability estimate of) recrudescence or new infection status in recurrent samples.</p>	<p>Same as minimal, with the addition of inference of the study-level corrected efficacy rate. Additional optimal components also include summary outputs, visualization</p>	<p>In the minimal case, individual recrudescence or new infection calls can be analyzed in a subsequent, separate workflow to generate</p>

		tools for the data and outputs, and testing datasets used for tutorials and validation.	corrected efficacy estimates (for example, Kaplan-Meier survival analysis). Integrated analysis of efficacy may provide more accessible, reproducible, and less biased estimates.
Input type	Processed allele call data generated by a typical genotyping assay used for TES (<i>e.g.</i> , length-polymorphic loci, microsatellites, or amplicon sequencing results) for participants with recurrent parasitemia. Missing data at any level (<i>e.g.</i> , for a given locus within a sample, or for an entire sample) are accepted.	<p>The framework can accommodate several genomic data types.</p> <p>The framework can also incorporate additional information that can be used to model uncertainty around allele calls, for example likelihood of false positive alleles from the allele-calling pipeline, parasite density or per-locus probability that a clone evades detection, complexity of infection, or data from intermediate time points.</p> <p>Additional non-genetic information that can be used to call recurrence, <i>e.g.</i>, day of failure / time-to-event analysis, and <i>a priori</i> information on likely failure rates based on previous studies.</p> <p>Outcome data for all participants, not just those with recurrent parasitemia, to allow inference of the study-level corrected efficacy rate.</p>	

Input format	Input data follows a format and structure clearly defined in the framework guidelines/tutorials.	Input data are in a universally recognized format for processed genotyping data that are made publicly available for external validation of results.	
Primary Output	Characterisation (yes/no classification or probability estimate) of recurrent parasitemia as recrudescence or new infection. Clear information is provided about what the different outputs are and where they are stored. If genetic data are uninformative (<i>e.g.</i> , no genetic diversity / all data are missing), the output is impartial (<i>e.g.</i> , the software refrains from classification / returns the prior probability).	Same as minimal, with the addition of inference of the study-level efficacy/failure rate estimate, with measures of uncertainty for the estimated corrected efficacy at different timepoints that account for censoring.	If recurrences are characterized using probability estimates, the probability estimates may be used to propagate classification uncertainty into efficacy estimation
Secondary Output	In addition to individual classifications, the tool can also output additional summaries of the data; for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Any observed matches (alleles considered the same) between paired samples for each locus - Estimated or observed COI for each sample - Allele composition and diversity for all loci 	Same as minimal, plus: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Probability of recrudescence for each pair - Estimated parameters (<i>e.g.</i>, sensitivity of allele detection) - Distributions of genetic distances between samples 	Assessment of genetic distances between pairs of samples aids in evaluating the strength of evidence. The distribution between pairs where samples are taken from different individuals can be used to construct a hypothesis test under a not-recrudescence null [cite Plucinski & Barratt 2021]. Secondary outputs may be of utility beyond direct interpretation of TES results. TES failure rate estimates for

			<p>sensitivity analyses (different allele frequency input) and consistency analyses (when analysis is based on 1,2,3...n loci, where n is the number of loci available). Failure rate estimates should ideally stabilize after several loci are analyzed, proving that estimates are not critically dependent on the number of loci. See Figure 2 in ⁸.</p>
Scalability	<p>The framework should handle various sample sizes, from small datasets to large-scale studies, and datasets of varied complexity, from low-complexity infections using data from few loci to high complexity infections with data from a large number of loci, with benchmarks for processing times.</p>	<p>Same as minimal, with effective parallelization (if needed) for very large datasets.</p>	
Hardware requirements	<p>The framework should be optimized for compatibility with standard computing devices commonly available to most users (<i>i.e.</i>, not require specialized hardware).</p>	<p>Same as minimal, with option of remotely hosted version on a virtual machine that can be freely accessed and used with only a web browser</p>	
Reproducibility	<p>External experts should be able to reproduce the same classification results using the genotyping data and data analysis scripts provided by the users</p>	<p>Same as minimal, and also including the ability of an external expert to reproduce the final efficacy estimates using the genotyping data, outcome data on all study participants, and analysis scripts provided by users.</p>	<p>Where appropriate, users should make all genotyping data and analysis scripts publicly available to allow external validation of results. For methods using stochastic algorithms, such as Markov Chain</p>

			<p>Monte Carlo, developers should specify a workflow users can follow to ensure they use an appropriate number of iterations per-chain and number of chains for reliable inference. Moreover, the workflow should record any seed(s) used to generate random numbers.</p>
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Table 6 - Characteristics of the statistical algorithm for the TES data analysis framework

Characteristic	Minimal Requirements	Optimal Requirements	Comments
Sensitivity and specificity	Account for following sources of error: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Genotyping errors, including nondetection of minority alleles (false negatives), miscalling of alleles, and artifactual alleles (false positives) - Chance matching of alleles in unrelated infections 	Same as minimal	
Accuracy	Characterisation of recurrent parasitemia should be unbiased (<i>i.e.</i> , not be biased towards either recrudescence or new infection) by factors that can be accounted for statistically, <i>e.g.</i> , genetic diversity, polyclonal infections, undetected alleles, and other genotyping errors. The method allows for missing data, <i>i.e.</i> , failed genotyping at one or more loci in a given sample.	The tool also includes the ability to estimate corrected efficacy rates based on data from all individuals and an underlying relatedness structure in the local parasite population with incorporated survival analysis to account for right censoring.	
Consistency	Characterisation of recurrent parasitemia, either categorically or with a probability, as recrudescence or non-recrudescence. Should become more accurate and provide a stable output as the number of input loci increases.	Minimal plus the algorithm performs internal cross-validation to confirm that the results are robust to sub-sampling of loci.	Internal validity requires that as data from more loci are included, confidence in the classification increases.